

"EVALUATION OF CEMENT NALA BUND PLUG"

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Abstract

A field study to evaluate the cement nala plug was carried out to study water storage characteristics in the cement nala plug by monitoring the depth of water storage in cement plug and length of water spread. The losses from surface water storage in the form of evaporation and seepage/percolation were estimated. The effect of seepage on ground water recharge was studied by monitoring water levels in the observation wells. Utilization of stored water in the cement nala plug was observed. The full water storage of cement nala plug was found to be 1525.91 m³, with the maximum length and width of spread, 96.4 m and 9.8 m. The maximum evaporation loss and seepage loss from the cement nala plug was found to be 271.47 m³ and 1147.23 m³, respectively. The impounded water in cement nala plug resulted in the increase in water levels in the observation wells of the influencing area.

Keywords: Cement Nala plug, Percolation, observation wells, maximum evaporation loss, Groundwater recharge

Introduction

The water conservation structures are integral part of soil and water conservation programmes and are important components of the watershed development and management programme. Conservation structures not only control the erosion and conserve water but also help in meeting the socio economical demands in various ways. Recharging of ground water storage can be effectively done by the construction of percolation ponds, nala bunding and cement nala plug to ensure sustained agricultural production under well command.

Water harvesting systems consist of collecting and storing the excess runoff from the catchment area of a watershed in a suitable reservoir and its subsequent use for irrigation of crops. It can be achieved by gully plugging, construction of structures like farm ponds, small check dams, nala bunds, percolation tanks etc.

Nala bunding is comprehensive activity. Nala bunds are embankments constructed across nalas for checking velocity of runoff, increasing water percolation and improving soil moisture regime. In fact, nala bund and percolation tanks both terms are synonymous but still they are being called differently at different places. However, the structures costing Rs. five lakhs or more are mostly called percolation tanks. Main objectives of nala bunding are to impound surface runoff coming from the catchments and to facilitate percolation of stored water into the soil sub-strata with a view to raise ground water level in the zone of influence of the nala bund.

Pendke (1997) studied the effect watershed management on ground water potential. The increase of 40 to 45 per cent in accumulated ground water potential due to watershed management practices was observed in the treated area after the period of four years. Gore and Naik (1995) studied Ground Water Recharge in Wagarwadi watershed through recharge process and ground water flow models. The soil and water conservation practices in the watershed have increased the soil moisture status and recharge of water in the wells. Patil (2009) evaluated the impact assessment of cement nala plug in Sonagaon-Bhanasgaon watershed of Osmanabad district was carried out during 2008-2009. Water storage characteristics of cement plug were studied by monitoring the depth of storage and length of water spread. The percolation of impounded water resulted in increased ground water table.

Materials And Methods

The area of watershed for one nala bund under study is 306 m².

Climate of study area

The climate of this region is tropical throughout the year. The average annual temperature in this region is 26.9°C. The average annual rainfall is about 700 mm. The south west monsoon is major source of rainfall for this region.

Soil characteristics

The topography of the watershed is flat type. The soil of this region is medium black. pH of the soil ranges from 6 to 8.

Crops grown in study area

Kharif crops like maize, sorghum, bajra, cotton etc. are grown in this area and also rabbi crop like wheat, gram etc. are grown in this area by the farmers. The farmers give supplemental irrigation for rabbi crops. About 1 to 2 irrigations are provided by nala bund for crops. About 5 to 6 ha land is irrigated with the help of nala bund.

Determination of water storage of nala bund at fortnight interval

For studying the water storage in cement nala bund, water level on the upstream of head wall of cement nala bund and length of water spread in the nala were recorded at fortnightly intervals to determine the changes in the stored volume of water.

For the determination of volume of water storage in nala at fortnightly intervals, the sections of nala bund at two different locations were measured by following standard method of cross-sectioning when nala was dry. Storage volume in nala was computed by taking the product of average of two cross-sections measured at embankment side and back water side and the distance between them. The cross-sections of water storage were varying at fortnightly intervals which were determined from cross-sections of nala bund and depth of water storage in nala bund.

The average length of impounding water was the length measured from upstream of the embankment of the nala bund to the back water spread.

i.e. average length of impounding water = L (m)

The average width is the average of width measured at the upstream of embankment side and back water side.

i.e. average width of impounding water = W

$$W = \frac{W_1 + W_2}{2} \quad \dots (1)$$

Where,

W₁ = width measured at embankment side

W₂ = width measured at back water side or back water width

The average depth is the average of depth measured at the upstream of embankment side and back water side.

i.e. average depth of impounding water = D (m)

$$D = \frac{D_1 + D_2}{2} \quad \dots (2)$$

Where,

D₁ = depth measured at embankment side

D₂ = depth measured at back water side or back water depth

The average cross-section of the impounding water at the upstream side of nala bund embankment is the product of average width and average depth.

i.e. average cross-section of impounding water = average width × average depth = W × D

$$\dots (3)$$

The total stored volume of the nala bund is the product of average cross-section and length between these cross-sections.

i.e. total stored volume = average cross-section \times average length
... (4)

Determination of evaporation losses from nala bund

Evaporation losses from nala were determined by considering the total water surface area in the nala at fortnightly intervals by taking widths of nala from cross-sections of the nala and the distance between them. The total evaporation losses were determined by considering daily evaporation rate with pan coefficient. Evaporation of water from the impounding water was calculated by following formula.

Surface area of water = Average width \times Average length
..... (5)

The volume of evaporated water from the surface area of impounding water was calculated by using following formula

Evaporation losses (m^3) = surface area (m^2) \times monthly evaporation rate (m)

... (6)

Average surface area of impounding water in nala bund for a month is measured by taking average of surface area measured at two fortnight interval of that month.

The monthly evaporation rate (MER) was calculated as

MER(m) = Daily evaporation rate ($\frac{m}{day}$) \times

No. of day in month (7)

The daily evaporation rate (DER) was calculated as

DER (m) = pan evaporation (m) \times pan co-efficient
.....(8)

Determination of seepage or percolation from the impounding water

The volume of water lost through seepage/percolation was computed by subtracting the evaporation losses and leakage losses plus taking two to five per cent loss was that part of water which might be used by animals for drinking, pesticide application and other uses from total stored volume of water in each nala at regular intervals.

Seepage + utility (m^3) = volume of impounding water(m^3) – evaporation losses(m^3)

Determination of impounding water on ground water recharge.

To study the influence of cement nala bund on water level in wells, two open wells were selected in the zone of influence i.e. well no.1 and well no.2 and two wells out of the zone of influence of cement nala bund i.e. at longer distance from the structure in the watershed i.e. well no.3 and well no. 4. The water surface elevation in each well with respect to full supply level of cement nala were determined by estimating the reduced levels of the fixed reference point marked on the top of each well by leveling elevations of water levels in the observation wells. Water surface in the cement nala bund for different periods were measured to study the effect of impounded water in cement nala bund on ground water.

The level of water in the four observations well is measured at monthly interval and graph is plotted taking head of water level on Y – axis and time interval on X – axis which shown the difference between water table fluctuation in the well under zone of influence and out of the zone. From these graphs shown the impact of impounding water in nala bund on ground water recharge.

Results And Discussion

Water harvesting and storage capacity of nala bund

During the study water harvesting and storage capacity of cement nala bund was estimated. The average length, width and depth of impounding water were recorded at fortnight intervals. The data is presented in observation table 1.

Table 1:- Average length, width depth and volume of impounding water at fortnight intervals.

Fortnight intervals	Average length (m)	Average width (m)	Average depth (m)	Volume of impounding water (m^3)	Average volume of impounding water (m^3)
I	82.4	8.4	1.2	830.592	572.983
II	72.5	7.5	0.58	315.375	
III	59.4	5.8	0.36	124.0127	588.168
IV	82.6	9.1	1.4	1052.324	
V	76.4	8.1	1.01	625.0284	443.1942
VI	72.6	7.5	0.48	261.36	
VII	96.4	9.8	1.8	1700.496	1398.705
VIII	86.1	9.1	1.4	1096.914	
IX	78.2	8.9	0.99	689.0202	506.905
X	69.4	7.8	0.60	324.792	
XI	55.6	7.7	0.38	162.6856	108.02
XII	45.6	6.5	0.18	53.352	

Fig.1 Evaporation loss per month

From table 1, It was revealed that the volume of impounding water was low in the month of June and July because initially the surface is dry and hence there are initial losses like infiltration, percolation etc. The maximum volume of impounding water i.e. $1398.705m^3$ was

observed in the month of September. The quantity of stored water i.e. impounded water in cement nala bund was drastically reduced after the month of November. A very little quantity of water ($108.02m^3$) was available in November. This is because of the stored or

impounded water lifted by the farmers for giving supplemental irrigation to rabbi crops.

3.2 Evaporation losses from water surface area

Table 2:- Volume of water loss in evaporation, seepage or percolation and Utility

Sr. No.	Month	Volume of impounding (m ³)	Evaporation loss (m ³)	Seepage + utility (m ³)	Utility (m ³)	Seepage/ Percolation (m ³)
1	June	572.983	154.48	418.503	19.22	399.29
2	July	588.168	104.13	484.038	9.8	474.24
3	August	443.1942	81.42	361.7742	62.82	298.95
4	Sept	1398.705	251.47	1147.23	70.70	1076.53
5	Oct	506.905	191.78	315.125	32.56	282.56
6	Nov	108.02	105.05	2.97	4.00	-1.03

The pan evaporation was measured at the mid of month and this reading taken for calculation of evaporation losses which are presented in table 2.

Fig 2 Average volume of impounding water per month

From Table 2 it was observed that the maximum evaporation was recorded in the month of September and the minimum evaporation was recorded in the month of August. As the evaporation rate is increasing since September, the depth of impounding ultimately the volume of impounding reduced since September and thus it would result in drying of water storage area after December. Another reason for dryness of storage area of cement nala bund is the excessive lifting of water for supplemental irrigation to crops. In the month of November and December the evaporation exceeds the volume of impounding water hence the seepage comes with negative sign.

Utility and seepage losses from the nala bund

The volume of water loss in seepage/percolation and utilized by farmers was computed by subtracting evaporation losses from the stored volume during corresponding monthly interval. The maximum stored water was available in August and September. The minimum seepage loss was observed in the month of November (-1.03m³) because of very less quantity of impounding water was remained in the nala bund and this water is used by farmer for supplementary irrigation for the rabbi crops like wheat, gram, maize etc. It was observed that in the fourth month maximum water was lost through seepage/percolation (1076.53m³) as the influence area was

completely dry hence infiltration capacity of the soil is maximum due to this reason the maximum percolation of water was occurred. This percolated water is meet to the ground water and increase the groundwater table. The maximum seepage losses particularly in the month of July-September (474.24-1076.53m³) were due to maximum water storage during that particular month and minimum evaporation losses in these months. The gradual reduction in seepage losses in subsequent months is due to reduction in storage volume of water in cement nala plug because of high evaporation and seepage losses.

3.4 Effect of impounded water on ground water recharge

To study the influence of cement nala plug on water level in wells, four open wells were selected in the zone of influence of cement nala bund i.e. at longer distance from the structure in watershed. The water level of each well in terms of depth was measured monthly from June to November with the help of tape by taking fixed reference point mark on the top of each well. Water surface in cement nala bund for different periods were plotted on graph to study the effect as impounded watering cement nala bund on GWR observations are represented in table 3.

Table 3: - Water levels in wells

Month	Treated area		Untreated area	
	Well no. 1	Well no. 2	Well no. 3	Well no. 4
June	3.5	2.5	1.3	1.9
July	5	6.3	2.9	3
August	7.5	8.8	5.2	5.8
September	11.0	11.3	6.9	7.5
October	10.1	10.9	6	6.3
November	9.3	9.8	5.2	5.9

Fig. 3:- Depth of water level in the observation well

Two wells were located in the vicinity of cement nala bund i.e. well no. 1 and well no. 2 in which initial depth of water in the well was found to be 3.5 m and 2.5 m. However, 2 wells were located in the untreated area i.e. well no.3 and well no. 4 in which initial depth of water in the well was found to be 1.3 m and 1.9 m considered for comparison of water table fluctuations. From the observation table no. 3 and Well water level graph it is revealed that the water table starts rising since mid June and attained its peak in September. The maximum water level was found in the month September. Maximum water level in observation well of treated area i.e. for well no.1 and well no.2 was found to be 11.0 m and 11.3 m respectively and for well in untreated area i.e. well no. 3 and well no. 4 was found to be 6.9 m and 7.5 m respectively.

This rise in water table is due to the rains received in the monsoon months. There was a steady decline in the water table up to November and then the water table has maintained a constant level up to the some extent.

Conclusions

1. The maximum capacity of nala bund was found to be 1398.705 m³ in the month of September and the quantity of impounding water drastically reduced after the month of November very little quantity of water remained in the nala bund.
2. The maximum length, width and depth of impounding water was found to be 96.4 m, 9.8 m and 1.8 m respectively.
3. The maximum evaporation loss was found to be 251.47 m³ in the month of September and minimum evaporation was found to be 81.42 m³ in the month of August. The maximum seepage or percolation was found to be 1076.53 m³ in the month of September.
4. The water level in the observation well under the zone of influence of nala bund have maximum water level i.e. 11.0 m and 11.3 m for well no. 1 and well no. 2, respectively. The water level in the well under the zone of influence is increases more than double that of well in untreated area.

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